

PROBLEMS OF THE INFORMATION WORLD AND THE INTERNET

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7569086>

Abstract. *When we talk about the informative world and the Internet, we must have an understanding of the Internet and information. Nowadays, it is difficult to comfort our lives without the Internet. Of course the Internet has opened the doors of a great opportunity for us, no one denies it. But as the coin has both sides, the Internet has its advantages and disadvantages. We mentioned this in this article. There are also problems and solutions in the information world.*

Keywords: *Internet, information, information, means of communication, large library, quality communication, business development, youth consciousness, negative situations, cybercrime, security, reliable information, subconscious impact, idleness, wasted time.*

When we talk about the informative world, naturally the question arises as to what the information is. Information is allocated to all information that the human senses receive. It means to convey or convey an opinion from the word "Information". Information can be used in different ways. Announcement of agreements between states and agreements. The fact that the organization changes the laws and regulations of the organization is also understood as information, information and transmission. Or there is no information about discussions between universities, muhukamas, solutions to important issues, and in writing. But the two are a very close concept. There are many types of information. For example: audio information, video information, textual information, graphic information, digital information. In addition, there are types of political information, social information, technical information and hoci. There are also features and qualities of information. Features, such as how to describe that information. Properties of Information:

- Expressed in letters
- Expressed in number
- Continuous formation
- More or less. And the quality:
 - How meaningful information is in the first place, in terms of meaning
 - Information is sufficiently fully covered
 - Reliability of information
 - Information stability Decrees and others.

Information is not a description of information, it refers to the relationship between information and the consumer. It does not make sense without consumer. The information is linked to the information only when it is mastered by the consumer. There are information units that measure information. This is a standardized rule.

Bit, byte, KB, MB, GB, TB, PT, ZT, YT.

Bits are accepted as the smallest unit of information. 1 byte - means 8 bits. 8 bits are required to encode all 256 characters on a computer keyboard. If we look at previous centuries, it was a very easy concept to express information. To date, the concept of information has been widely used in all fields, if it has studied nature, plants, fruits and animals and presented them and

presented them and presented them. For example, now there are more types of use, such as the study of some organization, factories, devices, the collection of technical and software information about them. Distributed information may be insignificant to someone. For example: you are on the road with the driver of the car, so (on the radio, on the anti-radar) you are warned not to increase speed, so the driver will be careful and vigilant. But a passenger in a car is ignored.

It is impossible to imagine the process of exchanging information or the process of obtaining information without the Internet. When we say Internet, a lot of people understand the www. This is called the whole world's cobweb. Internet (from Latin to network). This is an open system of information and information exchange. In this case, the data carrier protocol TCI / IP DIR. This protocol plays a key in the spread of data on the Internet. The 1st Internet was founded by the U.S. in the 1970s. This was a low level of development due to the war years. Then, gradually, data from one point to another began to develop. The Internet is the only system that has assembled computers into one point. The data was first exchanged between computers and later between the modem and the telephones. The Internet is a repository of world knowledge. Initially, it transmitted only textual data, but was gradually intended to send files such as picture and audio, which appeared in Switzerland in 1989. This is called the World Wide Web. The first Internet was organized, and then the WWW was organized. That is, this is the 1st part of the Internet (www). The reason for the U.S. military to create the Internet was to work even when there were networked networks during the war years. The most advanced time of the Internet was in the 1980s. Thus, the Internet has evolved around the world. Nowadays, everything we do is have an integral part of the Internet. Let's look at the internet connection. Cables, wireless, modem, Wi-Fi network, Internet cards, communication channel, optical fiber, satellite communication, radio channels, etc.

Cable connection - this is done through copper wires. Provides high-speed Internet access.

Optical fiber cable is a fiber-optic data. The main part of it is what we mentioned above. The top section used plastic protection. Currently, fiber-optic cables have increased and developed due to high-speed operation. For example, if there are 3 or 4 optical fibers inside a plastic-covered wire, each glass fiber (optical fiber) provides simultaneous conversations over 10 million phones and audio and video signals when the frequency is high. Examples of wireless data are simply our current mobile phones and computers. The process of sharing information with each other is carried out by radio logs. The development of the Internet has made our lifestyle much easier our lives. Simply put, you can easily share information (various information processes), do the things you need if you are standing, where you live, where your area is insignificant. Here are some useful and unnecessary aspects of the Internet.

1. You can find books all over the world.

The largest library is the largest library. You can find the book you want and want, the information you are looking for, everything you want in an instant. You can achieve the desired result without losing extra time, without spending on the way, without waiting queues. Of course, you have a computer or phone and antenna, and you have money in your account.

2. Plenty and diversity of the database.

Whether we call it a book in our school's library, from information in the Paris Library on the Internet, everything is available and the diversity of information is also noteworthy.

3. Not only information search but also quality communication is available on the Internet.

Now you can watch online with the popular Telegram, Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp and many governors.

4. Develop yourself.

You can learn to be the best in every field and study it online at home. At the same time, you can upload videos by watching videos or enriching your knowledge with information.

5. You can develop your personal block.

For example, you have groups in Telegram or chats with loved ones. You can create and distribute ads to them and talk to them with the field you need, or teach them to do good results by talking about them.

6. Reduces vacancies.

A person who is idle on the Internet can get a job by contacting them with a variety of advertising and a profession or field of interest. It will pay vacancies.

7. Availability of information about each field, each profession.

8. How many people keep data on the Internet. (based on cloud technology, etc.). 9. Renewing or organizing your personal business.

10. Convenience in all areas.

11. Freedom to comment.

12th. Hybrid system high.

13. Receive or provide technical support.

14. The news database is updated frequently.

15. Global communication.

16. 24/7 performance.

Disadvantages of the Internet.

- The negative impact of the Internet on the human body.
- Negative impact on young people's minds.
- Failure to be caused by Internet use.
- The lack of Internet culture in young people at all.
- Our information, personal information is not kept confidential.
- Plenty of cybercrime.
- Connection or technical problems.
- Availability of incorrect information as well.
- Being lazy using something ready, easy without hassle.
- Easy flight to the deception of bad and corrupt people.
- Search for reliable information.
- threat to life.
- Being connected to the Internet.
- The breakdown of peace.
- Psychologically a person's changes.
- All interests and desires are an integral part of the Internet, Telegram, etc.
- The transformation of life into a virtual world.

Now let's explain what we mentioned above:

Shameless videos, pictures. The abundance of immoral acts on social media. The lack of development and lack of understanding of spirituality and humanity in humans is upsetting. When we simply download a program to our smartphone or computer, we don't know that app asks us

for our personal information and only finds out that we can use it and use it and then use it. This is also part of a dangerous process. It is important to say that it is a tradition to deceive you through various phone numbers, links, audio, photo, video types, which are distributed by unsubstantiated individuals. Disruption or failure of our work weapon, low Internet or lack of antenna, etc. when working on the Internet. With a lot of information on the Internet, we need to know if it is well known. The competition will be strong. The use of the Internet, sitting in front of a computer, seems to be the norm, especially the young generation, which has a profound effect on their health and spirituality. Scientists say that since the younger generation has not yet formed ideological immunity, they will be able to teach destructive ideas and be involved in terrorist acts, and there will be a lot of belief. In such cases, we need to enrich the psyche and shape the spirituality. From an early age, we need to instill in them an understanding of who our ancestors were and who should have a suitable child for them. If we enrich and shape our beliefs about our religion, our beliefs, the above will not be observed. At the same time, there are many people sitting on the Internet day and night. Sitting on the Internet at night, the number of people greeting the day is growing. When I hear that, I get scared. Isn't the future of Uzbekistan in our hands? Shouldn't we and we contribute to the development and future of our state for tomorrow?! Shouldn't we make the most of our time without playing useful and useless games?! They say time is a flying car. Aren't we missing a lot of things without even realizing it? Each of us has to ask each of us every morning. We must set goals and objectives and move them forward. We need to protect ourselves from it without being in the Internet. On current social media, more than 60% of people sit in vain to spend time. If we are so indifferent, this indicator will increase in the next 2.3 years. People who are involved in the Internet and social network are even diagnosed with various new diseases. Nimophobia - fear of being left without the Internet. Igronomy is a link to computer games. This will not happen when we first understand what we have come to the world. We should not be left without the Internet or be left without a light, we should not be able to study in this world, be an ignorant, selfish person, and be afraid that our name will die without going into the world. We have to have our own place and our own way in this world!

Conclusion

The conclusion is that the Internet is not a deterioration of the media, because no one denies how much easier the Internet has made our lives. You just have to be more discriminating with the help you render toward other people. If we surf the Internet day and night, if we don't separate white from black, we'll be a mancont. So let's take advantage of everything on time. If we understand it, the Internet is a repository of information on the example of an inexhaustible treasure for us. We talked about how difficult the process of developing the Internet and the exchange of data is. What is the informative world? We found answers to the questions of what the problems were.

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